

VMAT versus DCAT radiotherapy planning in SBRT Lung

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Abstract

VMAT and DCAT radiotherapy plans were generated using Monaco 5.1 treatment planning system for seven I and II-stage Lung cancer patients. The study aims to compare the radiotherapy plan quality of the two treatment planning methods.

In the majority of cases, no significant difference was found in dose distribution at the OARs and in the dose spillage.

Introduction

During the VMAT treatments, the dose distribution is produced by moving the MLC leaves and by variation of the dose rate, while during the dynamic arc therapy (DCAT), the MLC leaves follow the shape of the PTV and the dose rate is modulated with the arc angle.

The study aims to compare the radiotherapy plan quality of the two treatment planning methods.

Materials and methods

Seven patients, clinical stage I and II, among them, 2 females were selected. The volume of the PTV, the location of the tumor, and the OARs being in the proximity of the PTV are summarized in Table 1. VMAT and DCAT SBRT radiotherapy plans were generated with the Monaco 5.1 treatment planning system. The beam setup was: three 6MV 220 degrees arcs with 0, 45, and 90 degrees collimator rotation as illustrated in Fig.1. and Fig.2.

The radiotherapy plans were evaluated with quantities based on the ProkKow System 2017 Radiosurgery Society Plan Study SBRT LUNG <http://proknowsystem.com/> summarized in Table 2.

	PTV volume cc	clinical stage	location		OAR	dose Gy	VMAT MU	DCAT MU
Male	22	I	Righth upper lobe	abutting the chestwall	Chestwall	4x12	3036	1963
Female	60	IIA	Left	periferial leison	Great wessels	4x12	3900	1988
Male	7,7	I	Righth lower lobe	abutting the chestwall	Chestwall	5x12	3512	1815
Male	119	IIA	Righth lower lobe	abutting the chestwall	Chestwall	6x10	3875	1463
Female	26,7	I	Left lower lobe	abutting the chestwall	Chestwall	4x12	2543	1555
Male	30	I	Left	periferial leison	Great wessels	4x12	3782	1513
Male	31	I	Left	central lesion		5x11	3518	1346

Table 1. The patient data

The quantities in Table 2. are pertained to 5x11Gy fractionation. Among the quantities, the dose covering 98% of the PTV, and the minimum dose to ITV were reduced in treatments, performed with 4x12Gy fractionation.

Protocol SBRT LUNG 5x11Gy

		protocol min	
Dose covering 98% Ptv	Gy	55	52,5
minimum dose to ITV	Gy	55	52,5
volume Heart covered by 10Gy	pc	0	10
Dose covering 0,03 cc Spinal canal PRV	Gy	7,5	20
Dose covering 0,03 cc Trachea Gy	Gy	10	40
Volume Total Lung-ITV covered by 20 Gy	pc	5	15
Volume Total Lung-ITV covered by 5 Gy	pc	10	30
mean dose Total Lung-ITV	Gy	5	10
volume Lung-R covered by 5 Gy	pc	0	30
volume Lung-L covered by 5 Gy	pc	0	30
Volume of the Thoracic wall covered by 30 Gy	pc	0	10
Dose covering 4cc of the Eosophagus	Gy	10	32,5
Dose covering 0,03cc of the Eosophagus	Gy	10	40
Dose covering 0,03cc of the Vessels	Gy	50	52,7

Protocol SBRT LUNG 4x12Gy

Dose covering 98% of PTV	Gy	48	45,7
minimum dose to ITV	Gy	48	45,7

Table 2. The quantities used for comparison of VMAT and DCAT plans.

Another significant factor in SBRT planning is the dose spillage outside the PTV. We investigated it with the Verisoft ver. 6.2 software (PTW, Freiburg, Germany) with obtaining lateral and vertical dose profiles and with comparison them.

Fig.1. VMAT dose distribution of patient #2.

Fig.2. DCAT dose distribution of patient #2.

Results

Fig.3. DVH graph of the VMAT (dotted) and the DCAT (solid line) plans of patient #2.

Patient number	#1	#2	#3	#4	#5	#6	#7
per protocol=pp, variation acceptance=va fail=f	VMAT/DCAT						
Dose covering 98% PTV (5x11)			pp/pp				pp/pp
Dose covering 98% PTV (4x12)	pp/pp	pp/pp		pp/pp	pp/pp	pp/pp	
minimum dose to ITV	pp/pp	pp/va	pp/pp	pp/pp	va/va	va/va	pp/pp
volume Heart covered by 10Gy	pp/pp	pp/pp	pp/pp	va/va	va/va	pp/pp	ff
Dose covering 0,03 cc Spinal canal PRV	va/va	pp/pp	va/va	va/va	pp/pp	va/va	va/va
Dose covering 0,03 cc Trachea Gy	va/va	va/va	pp/pp		pp/pp		
Volume Total Lung-ITV covered by 20 Gy	pp/pp	va/ff	pp/pp	va/va	va/va	pp/pp	pp/va
Volume Total Lung-ITV covered by 5 Gy	pp/pp	va/va	va/va	va/va	va/va	va/va	va/va
mean dose Total Lung-ITV	pp/pp	va/va	pp/pp	va/va	pp/pp	pp/pp	pp/pp
Volume of the contralateral Lung covered by 5 Gy	va/va	va/va	pp/va	va/va	va/pp	va/va	va/va
Volume of the Thoracic wall covered by 30 Gy	va/va	va/va		ff		pp/pp	pp/pp
Dose covering 4cc of the Eosophagus	pp/pp	pp/pp	pp/pp	va/va	pp/pp	pp/pp	va/va
Dose covering 0,03cc of the Eosophagus	pp/va	va/va	pp/pp	va/va	pp/pp	va/va	f/va
Dose covering 0,03cc of the Vessels	pp/pp	pp/pp				pp/pp	

Table 3. Correspondence of the quantities to the protocols. Pp= per protocol, va=variation, acceptance and f=fail

Table 3. shows the correspondence of the quantities to the protocol for the VMAT and for the DCAT plans. The majority of the VMAT plans and the DCAT plans fulfilled at least the variation acceptance level. In a few special cases, the quantities failed. The Thoracic wall dose exceeded the variation acceptance limit in both plans of Patient #4 with a large PTV volume. The total Lung-ITV dose limit was exceeded by 1% in the DCAT plan of Patient #2 with a large PTV volume. Overstep of the Heart dose volume limit by 1% of Patient #7 occurred.

Fig.4. Lateral dose profiles obtained from the VMAT (upper left) and the DCAT (lower left) dose matrices of patient #2.

For the investigation of the dose spillage, lateral and vertical dose profiles at the isocenter were obtained. Fig.4. Illustrates the lateral dose profiles obtained from the VMAT and the DCAT plans of patient #2. Good agreement in dose fall was found in almost all cases. The only difference in patient #3 was found. The small volume PTV was abutting the chest wall, the dose profile from the VMAT plan showed a steeper dose fall in Thoracic wall compared to one from the DCAT plan. Table 1. also shows the MU-s to administer the VMAT and the DCAT plans. To administer the DCAT plans significantly lower MU-s was needed than the VMAT plans.

Conclusion

The DCAT planning could be an alternative to the VMAT planning, especially for larger and symmetrical PTVs, and if OARs are not present close to the PTV. The DCAT plans have the advantage of significantly lower MU-s to administer the dose compared to the VMAT ones. If the PTV volume is small, or dose restrictions are needed to spare the OARs being close to the PTV, the VMAT plan was found superior.

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Appendix

Patient number		#1		#2		#3		#4		#5		#6		#7											
		VMAT		DCAT		VMAT		DCAT		VMAT		DCAT		VMAT											
		Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy	Gy		Gy								
	per protocol=pp, variation acceptance=va																								
Dose covering 98% PTV (5x11)	Gy	55	52,5					61,2	58,8	pp/pp															
Dose covering 98% PTV (4x12)	Gy	48	45,7	48	48,4	pp/pp	47	47,7	pp/pp		46	47,6	va/va	47,1	47,6	va/va	47,1	47,2	va/va	52,7	52,5	pp/pp			
minimum dose to ITV (5x11)	Gy	55	52,5					64,2	62,8	pp/pp											58,1	58,3	pp/pp		
minimum dose to ITV (4x12)	Gy	48	45,7	57,7	57,6	pp/pp	53,5	52,1	pp/va		62	51,7	pp/pp	50,5	51,5	pp/pp	53,1	51,7	pp/pp						
volume Heart covered by 10Gy	pc	0	10	0	0	pp/pp	0	0	pp/pp	0	0	pp/pp	7,10%	6,70%	va/va	1,60%	2,10%	va/va	0	0	pp/pp	11,10%	11,70%	fff	
Dose covering 0,03 cc Spinal canal PRV	Gy	7,5	20	9,1	8,9	va/va	1,3	1,2	pp/pp	8,2	8,9	va/va	10,4	9,6	va/va	3	5,8	pp/pp	7,8	7,4	va/va	12,3	13,7	va/va	
Dose covering 0,03 cc Trachea Gy	Gy	10	40	10,3	10,7	va/va	12,0	9,90	va/va	7,3	7,7	pp/pp				4,7	7,5	pp/pp							
Volume Total Lung-ITV covered by 20 Gy	pc	5	15,2,20%	3,20%		pp/pp	14,00%	16,00%	va/va	4,30%	2,50%	pp/pp	7,00%	8,00%	va/va	9,00%	8,10%	va/va	4,10%	4,60%	pp/pp	4,30%	5,05%	pp/va	
Volume Total Lung-ITV covered by 5 Gy	pc	10	30,6,70%	8,80%		pp/pp	33,00%	34,00%	va/va	19,80%	13,00%	va/va	27,00%	29,00%	va/va	13,5%	16,3%	va/va	12,4%	12,7%	pp/pp	20,20%	21,80%	va/va	
mean dose Total Lung-ITV	Gy	5	10	1,8	2,2	pp/pp	7,5	7,9	va/va	0,8	0,7	pp/pp	5,6	6	va/va	0,27%	3,4	3,7	pp/pp	3,1	3,2	pp/pp	3,9	4,3	pp/pp
Volume of contralateral Lung covered by 5 Gy	ppcc	0	30	0,40%	2,30%	va/va	5,1%	9,90%	va/va	0,00%	0,10%	pp/va	6,3%	7,7%	va/va	0,27%	0,00%	va/va	7,90%	4,4%	va/va	7,40%	10,10%	va/va	
Volume of the Thoracic wall covered by 30 Gy	pc	0	10	5,9%	9,10%	va/va	3,80%	8,90%	va/va	0	0	11%	12%			fff	7,6%			0	0	pp/pp	3,63%	3,95%	pp/pp
Dose covering 4cc of the Esophagus	Gy	10	32,5	6,1	8,3	pp/pp	7,6	10,1	pp/pp	3,9	3,3	pp/pp	10,5	10,1	va/va	3,3	4,3	pp/pp	8,2	8,4	pp/pp	21,9	19,4	va/va	
Dose covering 0,03cc of the Esophagus	Gy	10	40	8,5	10,5	pp/va	12	14	va/va	5,6	5,4	pp/pp	14,4	14,7	va/va	5,3	8,1	pp/pp	11,9	11,4	va/va	32	24	fva	
Dose covering 0,03cc of the Vessels	Gy	50	52,7	8,6	7,2	pp/pp	25,8	31,9	pp/pp	30									22	23,4	pp/pp	30			

Table 4. The values of the quantities for comparison of the two treatment methods.